

Model-Experiment Correlation for Mode I Interlaminar Toughening of Composite Interfaces Reinforced with Aligned Carbon Nanotubes

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SUMMARY

Aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) oriented perpendicular to the ply interface of laminated advanced composites have been shown to enhance interlaminar toughness. A previously developed model for Mode I toughness is used to understand its predictive capability. Recent representative Mode I interlaminar resistance-curves are compared to the predictive model for a woven laminated composite with aligned-CNT reinforcement.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, hybrid composites, polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), toughness, critical strain energy release rate

INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar properties in advanced laminated composites severely limit the overall performance of these systems, particularly problematic are delaminations caused by many sources including transverse impact. Interface damage such as delamination can drastically reduce the overall mechanical properties of the composite. In order to avert these failure mechanisms, several solutions have emerged: 3D-braiding, weaving, stitching and z-pinning, all of which reinforce the composite in the perpendicular direction with micron-diameter advanced fibers in bundles or pins with lengths on the order of millimetres [1]. The main drawback of these solutions is that there is an unavoidable, and oftentimes significant, reduction of the in-plane mechanical properties due to lamina fiber damage, stress concentration, and loss of in-plane volume fraction.

Z-direction reinforcement using forests of aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in between the plies of a composite are an alternative that may avoid reductions in in-plane properties. Interlaminar strength is thus increased by the reinforcement in the z direction, and crack growth is forestalled by a “pinning” mechanism that occurs between the plies [2]. Aligned-CNT reinforcement of this type has been previously implemented in two prepreg systems in a ‘nanostitch’ architecture (see Fig. 1) and also in a ‘fuzzy-fiber’ reinforced plastic (FFRP) architecture (see Fig. 2) [3-5]. The FFRP system is the focus of the current work, as representative Mode I resistance- (R-) curves, as well as fracture

surface SEMs are available for analysis. As can be seen in the micrographs, aligned CNTs are visible on the fracture surface after the mechanical tests (Fig 1). Observations of the fracture surfaces are used as inputs to the model and correlations drawn. A significant improvement is predicted with CNTs as compared to mm-scaled pins due the larger surface area of the CNTs. A strong dependence of the aspect ratio of the reinforcing fibers, favoring nanoscale reinforcement, is one conclusion that can be drawn from the model.

Figure 1. Illustration of a CNT-bridged ('nanostitched') prepreg specimen. A. Vertically-aligned CNTs (VACNTs) placed in between plies of a laminated composite. B Load displacement curve of a mode I 24 layer CF/epoxy/CNT prepreg C. Close-up of the crack, showing VACNTs bridging the crack between the two plies. D. Fracture surface of tested specimen.

Crack bridging due to the aligned CNTs may be modelled as a cohesive zone wherein the CNTs act like interlaminar z-direction pins or interlaminar 'nanostitches' to toughen the interface [3, 4, 6]. As the crack progresses, the stitches are sequentially slid out of the matrix until they are pulled free. Since fracture model is independent of the scale of the reinforcement, it may be applied to both CNT and larger scale (z-pin and stitching) reinforcement. In the case of multi-walled CNTs (MWNTs), a sword and sheath mechanism is added to the model, wherein the inner tube of the CNT is pulled out of the external shell in our recent work with a closed-form solution to this type of bridging [7].

EXPERIMENTAL

Mode I samples of the FFRP architecture are fabricated by first growing CNT forests on woven alumina fiber plies. Previous work chronicles the development of a CNT growth method using chemical vapour deposition (CVD) that grows radially aligned CNT forests on every fiber surface [8-10]. As pictured in Figure 3, large 15-cm long plies are processed in this way yielding CNT forests that are ~40 μm long grown on the fiber

surfaces. Multiple fuzzy fiber plies are impregnated with epoxy and stacked via hand layup, and cured into laminates [4, 11].

Figure 2. Illustration of fuzzy-fiber reinforced plastic (FFRP). A. Radially aligned CNTs on advanced fibers bridge interlaminar and intralaminar matrix regions. B. SEM image of CNTs grown on surface of alumina ceramic fibers.

Figure 3. Fuzzy fiber ply (left) and FFRP DCB specimen (right) reinforced in bending with (red) fiberglass plates.

Mode I fracture toughness was determined using a double cantilevered beam (DCB) specimen as specified in ASTM Standard D5528 for Mode I fracture [12]. A DCB specimen is pictured in Figure 3, sandwiched by (red) fiberglass plates to reinforce against excessive bending and bending failure. Sample R-curves are shown in Figure 4 for baseline (no CNTs) and FFRP specimens

Figure 4. Experimental Mode I R-curves of a baseline (no CNTs) and FFRP laminate.

When modelling crack propagation in the FFRP architecture, there is some ambiguity as to the crack path in relation to the radially-aligned CNTs. The theoretical maximum pullout length is the height of the CNT forest. CNT visualization under SEM after crack propagation (see Figure 5) allows estimation of CNT lengths that pullout of the matrix. In this particular image, a maximum CNT fragment of 3 μ m in length can be seen, suggesting an upper bound of CNT length of 3 μ m. Careful observation of these micrographs can lead to more accurate quantifications of CNT length as well as an estimation of the CNT volume fraction that participates in resisting crack propagation in the FFRP system.

Figure 5. SEM images of the FFRP fracture surface. CNTs of various lengths are observed to be pulled out of the crack faces.

MODELING

The model is divided into two parts. The first is determining the steady-state toughness improvement from either the pullout or sword-in-sheath mechanisms, and the second develops a solution for the full R-curves of the CNT bridging toughening. Pulling the CNT out of the matrix and pulling inner CNT walls from outer CNT layers both create a closure traction denoted as $p(x)$ that depends on the surface area of the embedded CNT, the volume fraction of CNTs across the crack interface, and the sliding shear stress between the CNT and the matrix, or between adjacent CNT walls (sword-in-sheath). The factor limiting pullout is CNT fracture, which happens when the stress in an individual CNT exceeds the strength. Once the outer shell of the CNT breaks, the CNT still produces toughening with the friction between the walls as the inner CNTs are slid out of the outer (broken) CNT shell (sword-in-sheath toughening mechanism in multi-walled CNTs [13]). The non steady-state solution [7] is not considered here.

Using the J-integral, as developed in [7], steady state fracture toughness improvement for both pullout and sword-in-sheath modes can be derived in closed form. The enhancement in toughness is given by the ratio of the steady-state toughness (G_{ss}) to the toughness of the interface without bridging reinforcement (G_0):

$$\frac{G_{ss}}{G_0} = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{L_f}{r_f} \right) \left(\frac{v_f \tau L_f}{G_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where L_f , r_f , and v_f are the length, radius, and volume fraction of the fiber, and τ is the interfacial (sliding) shear stress between the reinforcing fiber and the polymer matrix [14]. The scale dependence of the fiber, given by the inverse of the aspect ratio, on toughening favors small radii fibers such as CNTs. Limiting the toughening is the strength of the reinforcing fiber, which suggests that nanoscale fibers of high strength (such as CNTs) are ideal bridging elements for toughness enhancement. Equation (1) applies to both the pullout and sword-in-sheath mechanisms.

The model as described above allows the toughening effect with regard to fiber parameters, in particular the effect of scale, to be studied. The dependence of steady-state toughness on the geometric parameter r/L_f^2 is shown in Fig. 6. Reinforcement by CNTs provides $\sim 7X$ the toughening of z-pins, all other parameters being equal (see discussion in [7]). The accuracy of the model can be validated by comparing results to macroscopic z-pinned tests performed by Partridge *et al* [15]. Good agreement between the model and experimental data is noted, as seen in Figure 7, including the magnitude of the steady-state toughness as well as the non steady-state response (including the crack length to steady-state toughening, Δa_{ss}). The model for stitching pullout can be applied to nanoscale CNTs as well, but must be appropriately limited by CNT strength as mentioned earlier, wherein a regime is entered that has only sword-in-sheath toughening from the CNTs. It should be noted that interlaminar tensile and shear strength will be influenced by different mechanisms than the pullout toughening mechanism modeled here. Interlaminar shear strength has been measured to be enhanced when aligned CNTs are incorporated into the interlaminar region for the FFRP architecture [4].

Figure 6. Fracture toughness improvement for constant G_0 , v_f , and τ_c . (from [7]).

Figure 7. Z-pinning experimental data [15] and theoretical model comparison (from [7]).

Implementing the model to include characteristics of the FFRP architecture including the SEM visualization allow prediction of steady-state toughening. Toughening from the theoretical case of pullout of every fiber (CNT) would provide an upper bound, while the case of every CNT breaking and unsheathing will give a lower bound. It is expected that, due to the complex structure of the fracture surfaces and CNT morphology, both toughening mechanisms are operating. Other FFRP-specific mechanisms may also be operating, but only CNT pullout is modeled here. Toughening mechanisms inherent to

the alumina-fiber weave and epoxy system can be incorporated into the predicted steady-state toughness by observation of toughening in experimental baseline G_I curves. In the representative curves in Figure 4, an increase of $\sim 1 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ can be seen between G_0 and G_{ss} of the baseline specimen. Therefore, given an experimental G_0 of the FFRP laminate of $\sim 1.5 \text{ kJ/m}^2$, toughening of the FFRP system can be predicted by the addition of the effects seen in the baseline specimens and toughening predicted by the closed-form solution of CNT bridging. The effect of CNT pullout length and CNT volume fraction on the predicted steady-state toughness is presented in Fig. 8. Both longer CNTs and higher volume fraction, as expected, enhance steady-state toughening per equation (1). A volume fraction (V_f) of 1% has been implemented as the nominal value in the FFRP specimens, and SEM visualization presented here indicates that L_f (fiber pullout length) is between 1-3 microns in some cases. These nominal values give a reasonable prediction of the steady-state toughness (see Fig. 8) where the data for this specimen agrees well with the model for a CNT pullout length (L_f) of between 5-10 microns.

Figure 8. Comparison between experimental FFRP R-curve and the model prediction for steady-state toughening varying CNT length (left) and CNT volume fraction (right).

Nominal values for $V_f = 0.6\%$ and $L_f = 1-3 \mu\text{m}$.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Closed-form solutions that incorporate laminate and CNT characteristics from recently tested laminates reinforced with aligned CNTs can estimate bounds on Mode I steady-state fracture toughness enhancement. Increased bridging across crack tips is modeled by two mechanisms, CNT pullout from the matrix or sword-in-sheath pullout. Experimentally, it is likely that both mechanisms and perhaps others are operating to provide enhanced toughness, but the experimental-model correlation shows that for observed values of CNT pullout length and baseline toughening, the model is in good agreement with data available to date. Future work includes an expanded experimental fracture dataset, more detailed crack surface visualization, and model-experiment correlation of a fuzzy-fiber composite processed via infusion that has recently been demonstrated.

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